

Gating Springs: Conceptual Insights Derived From NOMPC

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Abstract. Cochlear mechanics converges on elastic gating springs that pull open mechano-electrical transduction (MET) channels. These gating springs are usually associated with force-conveying tethers, in particular hair cell tip links. That gating springs are tethers seemed supported by the *Drosophila* MET channel NOMPC, whose ankyrin repeat domain (ARD) forms a force-conveying tether and assumes a helical structure reminiscent of a spring. By combining protein domain duplications with mechanical measurements and electrophysiology, we now found that the NOMPC gating spring is a short intramolecular linker that is interspersed between ARD and gate. This molecular identification of a gating spring has implications on our general understanding of such springs, some of which are outlined here. Technical and conceptual aspects are discussed, and it seems that when shifting focus from tethers to the MET channels, we can find the hair cell gating spring.

INTRODUCTION

MET channels are force-gated ion channels that transduce mechanical stimulus force into ionic currents [1]. The gating spring model posits that force gates such channels by deforming elastic elements, the gating springs [2-6]. This gating spring-activation introduces a nonlinear gating compliance in the mechanics of both the sensory hair bundles of inner-ear hair cells [4,7,8] and the *Drosophila* ear [9,10]. Describing these nonlinear compliances with the gating spring model [4,5] allows to deduce the combined gating spring stiffness and the channel number and, thus, the effective stiffness of the gating spring per channel.

In hair cells, tip links seem predestined to serve as the gating springs, though they might be too stiff [11]. Alternative gating spring candidates include the tip link component protocadherin-15 [12,13] and ankyrin [14], which, in the nematode *C. elegans*, seems to convey force to a MET channel complex that resembles that of hair cells with respect to its molecular composition [15,16]. The idea that ankyrin repeats might form gating springs was inspired by the *Drosophila* MET channel NOMPC. The ankyrin repeat domain (ARD, Fig. 1) of this transient receptor potential (TRP) channel forms a one-turned helix [17,18], suggesting that it functions as a gating spring (Fig. 1A). In line with such function, the ARD was found to form a force-conveying tether [19] that, anchoring the channel intracellularly on microtubules [19-21], is required for the mechanosensory function of NOMPC [21]. A nonlinear gating compliance that requires NOMPC is seen in the fly's auditory mechanics [22], signaling that NOMPC gating involves a gating spring [23]. We now tested how molecular manipulations affect NOMPC function and this gating compliance, revealing that the NOMPC gating spring is not its ARD, but a short linker between ARD and gate (Fig. 1B). Here, we explore what this little linker might tell us about gating springs in general and, more specifically, about the hair cell gating spring.

FIGURE 1. The NOMPC gating spring. A. Previous model, in which the ARD serves as the gating spring. B. New model, in which the gating spring is a small linker between ARD and channel gate. MT: microtubule. For NOMPC activation by pushing force, see [24].

Gating Springs Are Tractable Genetically

The amino-terminal ARD of NOMPC is connected to the transient receptor potential (TRP) domain and the pore-forming transmembrane helices by a short linker element. Protein domain duplications revealed that linker governs native gating spring mechanics, contributing more than 90% of the intrinsic elasticity of the NOMPC gating spring. Hence, a short peptide can govern gating spring mechanics and, thus, act as gating spring. If gating spring mechanics would report the physical properties of membrane lipids or several structural elements, tracing them down would be more challenging.

Gating Springs Can be Compact Compliant Elements

A gating spring can be illustrated as a coil spring that is arranged in series with the channel gate [4,5,26] (Fig. 1). Our findings on NOMPC support such arrangement and also basic assumptions of the gating spring model [4,5], including their Hookean behavior of the gating springs and their association with individual MET channels. Rather than deforming longitudinally like a simple coil spring, however, the NOMPC gating spring seems to behave like a hinge. Hence, gating springs may not necessarily be coil springs – they can be more compact compliant elements.

Simple Stiffness Comparisons May Not Suffice for Delineating Gating Springs

Describing gating compliances with the gating spring model allows to deduce the combined gating spring stiffness K_{GS} , projected to the mechanics of e.g. the hair bundle, and the channel number N [4-6, 25]. The ratio $\gamma^2 \kappa = K_{GS}/N$

is the effective stiffness of the gating spring per channel, i.e. its spring constant κ times the squared geometric projection factor $= x/X$, which relates hair bundle displacements (X) to the deformation of the gating spring (x) [4-6, 25]. For hair cells, γ can be estimated from the average distance between adjacent stereocilia and the hair bundle height, assuming that the tip link is the gating spring [4,5]. This yields values of κ around 1 pN/nm, allowing to search for structural elements that, judging from their stiffness, might function as gating spring. Such reasoning seems somewhat circular because the search by itself acknowledges that the tip link might not be the gating spring. Even if the gating spring is known, the projection factor γ might remain unknown, and all that can be deduced is $\gamma^2\kappa$, the effective gating spring stiffness. Hence, to delineate gating springs, we need to explore how molecular manipulations alter this stiffness and the mechanosensitivity of the channel and cells.

Gating Springs Should Be Small and Close to Channel Gates

That the NOMPC gating spring is not its large ARD, but a tiny linker between ARD and gate, seems advantageous mechanistically. Being close to the gate, this linker can take up channel gating movements directly, without handing them over to the ARD. This reduces the load the gate has to move when opening and closing, especially because the linker itself seems small and light. As a consequence, the channel can gate with high energy-efficiency, facilitating the fast and sensitive transduction of soft stimuli. Given this advantage, we anticipate that, rather than being prominent protein tethers, gating springs have to be inconspicuous linker elements sitting right next to ion channel gates. Mechanosensory transduction in hair cells may not be optimized for energy-efficiency [27], yet the single gating energy $E = 1/2 \kappa x^2$ of the hair cell MET channel (ca. 7-9 zJ [4,16]) that can be deduced using the gating spring model closely resembles that of NOMPC (ca. 10-13 zJ [10]).

Bringing Together Spring and Gate

By flexibly suspending the gate on the AR domain, the NOMPC gating spring provides the structural flexibility the gate requires to open and close, and we think this is a general theme. To switch conformation locally and transiently, ion channel gates have to be suspended elastically, and, to enable efficient gating, that gate suspension has to be the most elastic force-transmitting element, the gating spring. If the NOMPC ARD or a hair cell tip link were more compliant than that suspension, the stimulus force would mainly deform those structures, but could hardly open the gate. If the NOMPC gating spring were its ARD, mechanical stimuli would mainly perform mechanical work on the ARD, without opening the channel gate. Likewise, if the hair cell gating spring were the tip link or an ankyrin tether, mechanical stimuli would mainly deform those tethers, but could hardly open the gate. Hence, instead of being tethers, it seems that gating springs have to be integral MET channel components that elastically suspend the gates of the channels, allowing the gates to switch conformation, and enabling effective gating by external stimuli.

MET channels can receive force from tether filaments (“force from filaments” gating) and the surrounding lipid bilayer (“force from lipids” gating) [28]. So far, gating springs had mainly been associated with tethers, and with MET channels that receive force from filaments [1,29,30]. Emancipating gating springs from tethers, the possibility arises that gating springs are basic ion channel components that enable gating, irrespective of whether a channel receives force from filaments or lipids, and irrespective of what induces the force.

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COMMENTS AND DISCUSSION

[Manuela Nowotny]: I like this nice overview of how NOMPC works. Since there are still two pages left, you could report more detailed about the integration of the channel into the sensory system of the sensory cells in insects and also discuss the controversy with other channels in the cilium.

[Martin Göpfert]: Not sure whether this the right place to address the seeming controversy concerning other TRP channels in the fly ear. NOMPC is the only TRP channel known to function as a mechanosensory transduction channel, whereas all the other TRPs that have been implicated into mechanosensation seem to act downstream of transduction channels (for a recent review, see [https://www.cell.com/trends/biochemical-sciences/pdf/S0968-0004\(24\)00114-2.pdf](https://www.cell.com/trends/biochemical-sciences/pdf/S0968-0004(24)00114-2.pdf)). Concerning the integration of the channel, I don't feel competent - all we know is that the NOMPC ankyrin domain interacts with microtubules, and that disrupting microtubules eliminates NOMPC mechano-gating. This is already mentioned in the MS.

[Anthony Peng]: What do you think is the elegant structure of the NOMPC ankyrin domain good for? It looks like a spring.

[Martin Göpfert]: My take is that this domain is important, and I also don't question that the tip link is important. The ankyrin domain is elastic, though being less elastic than the linker. Possibly, the ankyrin domain starts deforming once the linker is deformed in full, protecting the gate from mechanical disruption when forcing is intense. The domain might also be involved in modulating gating, and its elegant structure suggests that there might be more to it, even though it does not function as a gating spring.